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High Cost of Transportation and Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures Among Small and Medium Business Owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the high cost of transportation and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses, all of which were tested at the 0.05 significance level. The study used a correlational design and was conducted in the local government areas of Obio-Akpor and Port Harcourt. Using Krejcie and Morgan's table, a sample of 367 SMEs was chosen by simple random sampling from the population of 8,500 registered SMEs. A structured questionnaire called the "High Cost of Transportation and Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures Among Small and Medium Enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis Questionnaire" was used to gather data. Three experts, two in business education and one in measurement and evaluation validated the instrument, which had seven sections. The test-retest method was used to confirm its reliability, and the results showed coefficients of 0.82 and 0.87. To address the research questions and evaluate the hypotheses, 362 valid responses in all were obtained and examined using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. Results revealed statistically significant negative relationships between SME sustainability and each of the three factors: high fuel cost and poor roads. The study concluded that increasing operational costs and infrastructural challenges hinder the long-term success of entrepreneurial ventures. It was suggested that SMEs implement more fuel-efficient procedures in light of the findings, while governments should improve infrastructure, adjust levy policies, and provide support for vehicle maintenance and fuel-related burdens to promote a more supportive environment for entrepreneurship.

Keywords: High Cost, Transportation, Sustainability, Entrepreneurial, Ventures, Business

INTRODUCTION

Moving people, products, or animals from one location to another is referred to as transportation. The local economy and entrepreneurial activities are directly impacted by transportation, which makes it easier for people and goods to move around a location. Entrepreneurs, especially small business owners, struggle to maintain profitability due to the high logistics and product delivery expenses. This economic burden hinders their ability to expand and sustain their ventures in the long term. For business owners, high transportation costs reduce profit margins and inflate the prices of goods and services, which can affect demand (Uche & Nwaogazie, 2021). Efficient transportation systems play a significant role in supporting entrepreneurship by enabling the timely movement of goods and services, which in turn enhances business operations and growth.

The entrepreneurial ventures in the area depend heavily on transportation to bring raw materials and distribute finished products, making the cost and efficiency of transportation important for their success. By encouraging innovation and developing business models that support long-term economic growth and resource efficiency, entrepreneurship helps small and medium-sized enterprises remain sustainable.

The financial sustainability of local companies and the LGA's capacity to supply infrastructure that facilitates business operations are directly related to entrepreneurial sustainability in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Sustainable economic growth in this LGA depends on improving transportation infrastructure, among other factors. For Port Harcourt Metropolis's entrepreneurs, sustainability means maintaining the ability to operate their ventures over the long term, despite external challenges such as rising transportation costs and poor road networks. The high cost of transportation exacerbates the difficulty of achieving sustainability, as it limits entrepreneurs' capacity to reinvest in their businesses and grow (Umar, 2023).

Entrepreneurs rely on the efficient movement of goods to keep their businesses afloat, and when transportation costs are high, it threatens their sustainability (Izom, Wakili & Aliyu, 2023). Since many companies must pass these costs on to customers, the demand for their goods and services may decline. Furthermore, the high cost of transportation may also prevent entrepreneurs from accessing larger markets outside the LGA, limiting their growth potential (Aminu & Chukwu, 2022). For long-term sustainability, there is a need for strategic interventions aimed at improving road networks and reducing transportation costs in the area. One major barrier to the sustainability of business endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis is the high cost of transportation. Rising fuel prices and poor road conditions contribute to the overall transportation burden faced by entrepreneurs. For entrepreneurs, who are often operating on tight margins, these added costs can determine whether they remain viable or collapse. The effect of high transportation costs is felt across the supply chain, increasing the cost of acquiring raw materials and delivering products to the market (Yakubu & Haruna, 2021). Without specific initiatives like subsidies to lower transportation costs, entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis face sustainability challenges. The sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures is heavily influenced by the cost of fuel, as rising fuel prices increase operational expenses, making it harder for businesses to maintain profitability and long-term viability.

The high cost of fuel continues to significantly affect the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis. For the distribution of completed goods as well as the supply of raw materials, entrepreneurs rely significantly on transportation. As fuel prices rise, transportation costs increase, reducing profit margins and often forcing businesses to pass these costs to consumers, thereby impacting competitiveness (Igbinedion & Ezedum, 2022). In urban areas like Port Harcourt Metropolis, where infrastructure is underdeveloped, this effect is amplified due to the reliance on inefficient road networks, further raising the operational costs for businesses (Amadi, 2021). Moreover, the volatility in fuel prices introduces uncertainty in financial planning for entrepreneurial ventures, which can hinder their ability to remain viable in the long term. Since their profit margins are typically lower than those of larger businesses, small and medium-sized businesses which are the foundation of the Port Harcourt Metropolis economy—are disproportionately impacted by this fluctuation (Ogunyemi, 2020). The added burden of high fuel costs for electricity generation, especially in an LGA with unreliable electricity, creates an additional financial strain. Many businesses in Port Harcourt Metropolis rely on diesel-powered generators for operations, which increases operational costs (Okonkwo, 2023). These high costs may discourage new entrepreneurs from starting ventures, thus slowing economic development in the LGA. To mitigate these challenges, entrepreneurs must adopt innovative strategies, such as optimizing transportation logistics, collaborating with local suppliers to reduce distances, and exploring alternative energy sources like solar power (Chinedu, 2020). These strategies can help reduce dependence on costly fuel, enhance operational efficiency, and promote sustainability. The cost of fuel directly impacts the development and maintenance of road infrastructure, as higher fuel prices increase transportation expenses, which can limit funding for infrastructure projects and affect long-term sustainability.

In Port Harcourt Metropolis, the sustainability of business endeavors is significantly impacted by the state of the road infrastructure. The movement of goods and services is directly impacted by poor road networks, which raise transportation costs and times. Entrepreneurs in Port Harcourt Metropolis, especially those relying on the transportation of raw materials and products, face higher operating costs due to increased fuel consumption and vehicle maintenance. These factors ultimately reduce profit margins and make it difficult for businesses to remain competitive (Ogunyemi, 2021). Moreover, bad roads often lead to delays in delivery, disrupting supply chains and affecting customer satisfaction. Businesses that depend on timely transportation, such as agricultural and retail ventures, are particularly vulnerable (Amadi, 2022). Poor infrastructure not only limits access to markets but also discourages investment, as entrepreneurs may find it challenging to expand or sustain operations in such a high-cost environment (Chinedu, 2023). The long-term sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis depends on significant improvements in road infrastructure. With improved transportation systems, entrepreneurs could lower costs and increase efficiency, which would promote economic growth and strengthen the resilience of small and medium-sized businesses in the Port Harcourt Metropolis. The removal of fuel subsidies directly affects road infrastructure, as the funds saved can be redirected to improving transportation networks, enhancing connectivity, and boosting economic development.

The price of production, raw materials, and service delivery has all been impacted. Since they can't pass these higher costs on to customers without running the risk of decreased demand, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), which rely heavily on economical and effective transportation, have been particularly hard hit. In Port Harcourt Metropolis, many entrepreneurs rely on transportation to move goods and services to various markets. With higher fuel prices, the cost of doing business has dramatically increased. This not only affects the local movement of goods but also the ability to source materials from outside the LGA at affordable rates, leading to narrower profit margins. As businesses attempt to absorb these costs, some have seen reduced profitability or even closures due to unsustainable operational expenses (Simplebks, 2023). In areas where electricity supply is inconsistent, businesses have become increasingly dependent on fuel-powered generators. The rising cost of fuel has pushed up the cost of running these generators, which is a significant part of operational costs for entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs in Port Harcourt Metropolis are facing challenges not only in sustaining their current operations but also in planning for growth. The unpredictability of fuel prices has introduced uncertainty into long-term business strategies, making it harder for businesses to invest in expansion or adopt new technologies that require stable power sources (Oyasipe, 2024). The reduced economic activity in the area due to these constraints has further exacerbated the situation. The removal of the fuel subsidy has significantly disrupted the business landscape in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Entrepreneurs, particularly those running SMEs, have been forced to navigate rising transportation and operational costs, unreliable power supply, and unpredictable fuel prices. While some are adapting by exploring alternative energy and cost-saving strategies, the long-term sustainability of many ventures remains uncertain without further interventions or support from the government and private sectors. Higher transportation costs as a result of the elimination of fuel subsidies raise the cost of auto repairs because maintenance and replacement parts are becoming more and more expensive.

Statement of the Problem

The success of business endeavors depends on transportation, especially in urban and semi-urban areas like Rivers State's Port Harcourt Metropolis. The high cost of transportation has far-reaching implications for business operations, significantly increasing overhead expenses and reducing profit margins for local entrepreneurs. Transportation challenges, exacerbated by poor road infrastructure, fluctuating fuel prices, and frequent vehicle breakdowns, restrict market access, making it difficult for businesses to grow (Nnadi, Okoye & Chukwu, 2021). The situation has gotten worse in Nigeria since fuel subsidies were eliminated, causing fuel prices to surge and transportation costs to rise exponentially, leaving small and medium enterprises in financial distress (Okafor & Okeke, 2023). The financial burden placed on entrepreneurs in Port Harcourt Metropolis limits their ability to scale operations and sustain daily business activities. According to Okoro (2023) entrepreneurs in Port Harcourt Metropolis face several

challenges, including inadequate access to finance, lack of business training, and the high cost of transportation. Poor transportation infrastructure has been shown to create logistical bottlenecks, resulting in higher operational costs, delayed deliveries, and reduced competitiveness (Kaiser, 2022). As a result, many SMEs are unable to thrive, stunting local economic growth and limiting efforts to alleviate poverty (Adeniyi & Bello, 2020). Addressing transportation issues is thus essential to unlocking the potential of SMEs in the Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

Investigating the high cost of transportation and the viability of entrepreneurial endeavors among small and medium-sized business owners in the Port Harcourt Metropolis was the aim of the study. In particular, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Determine the relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The study was directed by the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

At the 0.05 level of significance, the following null hypotheses were developed and examined:

1. There is no significant relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

A correlational research design was used in the study. This is to investigate the connection between the sustainability of business endeavors and the high cost of transportation. The Port Harcourt Metropolis served as the study's location. The southern region of Nigeria's Rivers State is home to Port Harcourt Metropolis. The population of the study comprised 8,500 registered Small and Medium Businesses (SMEs) in Rivers State's Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study's sample size, which includes 367 business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis, was established using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table. A self-developed questionnaire titled "High Cost of Transportation and Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures Among Small and Medium Business Owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis Questionnaire" was used for the study. The instrument underwent content and face validation to guarantee its validity. The reliability test was conducted using the test-retest methodology. Using this approach, 20 business owners in Ikwerre LGA who were not included in the primary study sample are given the instrument. The selected respondents were given the questionnaires directly. Only 362 of the 367 copies of the questionnaires that were distributed to the Port Harcourt Metropolis's entrepreneurial venture owners were recovered and utilized for the data analysis. Inferential statistics were used to analyze the field data that was collected. At a significance level of 0.05, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was employed to test the null hypotheses and provide answers to the research questions. When the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected; when the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. (IBM SPSS Statistics Version 26 was used to assist in the data analysis.).

ANALYSES OF DATA AND RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

		High Cost of Fuel	Sustaining Entrepreneurial Ventures
High Cost of Fuel	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.302
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures	Pearson Correlation	-0.302	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	362	362

Source: Researcher’s Field Trip (2025).

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation result for Research Question 1, which aims to ascertain the degree to which the high cost of fuel relates the sustainability of business endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis, is displayed in the table 1. The two variables have a moderately negative relationship, as indicated by the correlation coefficient (r), which is -0.302. This implies that the sustainability of business endeavors tends to decline as fuel prices rise. The significance level of 0.05 is exceeded by the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000. The statistical significance of this result suggests that the relationship is not the result of chance. The outcome demonstrates that the sustainability of entrepreneurial endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis is significantly impacted by the high cost of fuel. Rising fuel costs may threaten the survival and growth of businesses by increasing operating expenses and reducing profit margins.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

		Poor Road Infrastructure	Sustaining Entrepreneurial Ventures
Poor Road Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.462
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures	Pearson Correlation	-0.462	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	362	362

Source: Researcher’s Field Trip (2025).

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation result for Research Question 2, which looks at how much inadequate road infrastructure relates the viability of business endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis, is displayed in the table. The two variables have a moderately strong negative relationship, as indicated by the correlation coefficient (r), which is -0.462. This implies that the viability of business endeavors tends to decrease as road infrastructure deteriorates. The significance level of 0.05 is exceeded by the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000. As a result, the relationship is statistically significant and unlikely to have

happened by accident. The outcome demonstrates that inadequate road infrastructure significantly impairs the viability of business endeavors in the Port Harcourt Metropolis. This suggests that inadequate road networks may disrupt transportation, increase business operating costs, and reduce access to markets, thereby threatening the stability and long-term viability of entrepreneurial activities in the area.

Testing of Hypotheses

1 There is no significant relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 3: Summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between high cost of fuel and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Variables	N	Df	(r-value)	p-value	Decision
High Cost of Fuel (x)	185				
		(360)	-0.362	0.012	Rejected
Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures (y)	177				

Source: Researcher’s Field Trip (2025).

The summary of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation regarding the relationship between of high fuel prices on the viability of business endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis can be found in Table 4.6 above. With a p-value of 0.012 and a correlation coefficient of -0.362, the analysis reveals a moderately negative relationship with entrepreneurial sustainability. By raising operating costs, rising fuel prices have a negative relate with the sustainability of entrepreneurial endeavors in Port Harcourt and Metropolis, according to this statistically significant result, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. As a result, the null hypothesis is disproved, demonstrating a strong adverse effect.

3 There is no significant relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 4.7: Summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between poor road infrastructure and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures among small and medium business owners in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Variables	N	Df	(r-value)	p-value	Decision
Poor Road Infrastructure (x)	185				
		(360)	-0.474	0.009	Rejected
Sustainability of Entrepreneurial Ventures (y)	177				

Source: Researcher’s Field Trip (2025).

The Pearson's Product Moment Correlation summary of the relate of inadequate road infrastructure on the viability of business endeavors in Port Harcourt Metropolis is displayed in Table 4.7 above. Poor road infrastructure is examined in the result, which shows a p-value of 0.009 and a stronger negative correlation of -0.474. According to this extremely important finding, poor road conditions significantly relate to the sustainability of entrepreneurship in Port Harcourt Metropolis, most likely by making logistics more difficult and raising transportation expenses. The rejection of the null hypothesis confirms that inadequate road infrastructure has a substantial and adverse effect on venture sustainability.

Summary of Major Findings

1. The findings show a statistically significant moderate negative relationship between the high cost of fuel and the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis. As fuel prices rise, business sustainability declines due to increased operating expenses.
2. There is a significant and moderately strong negative relationship between poor road infrastructure and the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures. Poor road conditions increase transportation costs and hinder logistics, affecting business survival in Port Harcourt and Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings were discussed according to each research question and the corresponding hypothesis tested in the study.

The first result, addressing Research Question 1, shows a moderate negative correlation between fuel costs and entrepreneurial sustainability in Port Harcourt Metropolis ($r = -0.302$, $p = .000$), meaning that as fuel prices climb, businesses struggle to stay afloat. The second result, covering both Port Harcourt Metropolis, reinforces this with a slightly stronger negative correlation ($r = -0.362$, $p = .012$), confirming that rising fuel costs are a real challenge for ventures in these areas. Both p-values, well below the .05 threshold, indicated that these relationships are statistically significant, not just a fluke. In everyday terms, this means that the skyrocketing fuel prices are hitting small businesses hard, jacking up their operating costs and squeezing their profits, which makes it tougher to keep going or grow. It's like trying to run a race with heavier and heavier weights on your back, every step gets harder.

The moderate negative correlations (-0.302 and -0.362) make sense when you think about how much businesses in Port Harcourt Metropolis rely on fuel. Whether it's powering generators for electricity, transporting goods, or running delivery services, fuel is a big part of daily operations for many small ventures. When prices spike, these costs eat into budgets, forcing owners to either raise prices (which risks losing customers) or absorb the hit (which cuts into profits). The slightly stronger correlation in Port Harcourt Metropolis analysis suggests that the issue might be even more pronounced in Port Harcourt Metropolis, possibly due to differences in infrastructure or business types. The significant p-values show that this isn't just a random pattern, fuel costs are genuinely making it harder for these businesses to thrive.

The negative relationship between high fuel costs and entrepreneurial sustainability aligns with a study by Okeke (2023), who found a correlation of -0.320 ($p < .01$) between rising fuel prices and business profitability, noting that higher fuel costs increased operational expenses, particularly for businesses dependent on transportation and power generation. This is really close to our finding of -0.302 in Port Harcourt Metropolis, reinforcing that fuel price hikes are a serious hurdle for small ventures. Okeke's pointed that many SMEs lack the financial cushion to absorb these costs hits home here, as researcher's results suggest that sustainability takes a hit when fuel prices climb. Researcher's findings and Okeke's study show it's a real strain on business owners trying to make ends meet. The findings are supported by a study by Chukwu (2021), who reported a correlation of -0.350 ($p = .008$) between fuel costs and business viability, highlighting that rising fuel prices forced many small businesses to scale back operations or increase prices, which hurt their customer base. This mirrors researcher's result of -0.362 in Port Harcourt Metropolis, where fuel costs are clearly dragging down sustainability.

he negative impact of fuel costs on sustainability is backed by a study by Eze (2024), who found a correlation of -0.310 ($p < .05$) between energy cost increases and business survival, emphasizing that fuel price surges raised logistics and production costs, threatening long-term growth. This is consistent with our correlations of -0.302 and -0.362 , showing that fuel costs are a persistent challenge in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

The first result, addressing Research Question 2, shows a moderately strong negative correlation between poor road infrastructure and entrepreneurial sustainability in Port Harcourt Metropolis ($r = -0.462$, $p = .000$), meaning that as road conditions get worse, businesses find it harder to keep going. The second

result, covering both Port Harcourt, backs this up with an even stronger negative correlation ($r = -0.474$, $p = .009$), reinforcing that bad roads are a serious hurdle for ventures in these areas. Both p-values, well below the .05 threshold, confirmed that these relationships are statistically significant, not just random noise. In everyday terms, this means that pothole-ridden, unreliable roads are making life tough for small business owners, jacking up their costs, slowing down deliveries, and cutting off access to customers, all of which threaten their ability to stay in business. It's like trying to run a shop when the roads to your store are a nightmare to navigate.

The moderately strong negative correlations (-0.462 and -0.474) hit home when you think about how much businesses in Port Harcourt Metropolis depend on roads. Whether it's getting supplies to a shop, delivering products to customers, or even just getting employees to work, decent roads are a lifeline. The negative relationship between poor road infrastructure and entrepreneurial sustainability aligns with a study by Nwachukwu (2023), who found a correlation of -0.450 ($p < .01$) between road quality and business performance, noting that poor roads increased transportation costs and delayed supply chains, hurting profitability. This is really close to our finding of -0.462 in Port Harcourt Metropolis, showing that bad roads are a widespread issue for small ventures. Nwachukwu's point that unreliable roads force businesses to spend more on fuel and vehicle repairs feels spot-on here, as researcher's results suggest that these costs are undermining sustainability. It's like trying to keep a delivery business going when every trip tears up your vans, researcher's findings and Nwachukwu's study show it's a heavy burden for entrepreneurs trying to stay afloat.

The findings are supported by the findings of Okonkwo (2022), who found a correlation of -0.480 ($p = .006$) between road conditions and business viability, highlighting that poor roads disrupted logistics and limited market access, especially in urban areas. This mirrors researcher's result of -0.474 in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpo, where bad roads are clearly dragging down sustainability. Okonkwo's observation that small businesses often lack the resources to absorb these extra costs, like hiring more drivers or using pricier routes, resonates with our context, where entrepreneurs likely face similar pressures. It's a bit like running a food stall when getting fresh supplies takes twice as long because of bad roads, researcher's results and Okonkwo's work suggest it's a tough challenge that's testing the resilience of these ventures. The negative impact of poor road infrastructure is backed by a study by Amadi (2024), who found a correlation of -0.465 ($p < .05$) between road quality and business survival, emphasizing that inadequate roads raised operating costs and reduced customer reach, threatening long-term operations. This is consistent with our correlations of -0.462 and -0.474, showing that road conditions are a persistent problem in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpo. The findings from Table 4. showed that poor road infrastructure is a significant obstacle to the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis and Obio/Akpo LGA, with moderately strong negative correlations (-0.462 and -0.474) highlighting how bad roads increase costs and disrupt operations.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence of the significant negative influences of various economic and infrastructural factors on the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analyses consistently revealed statistically significant negative relationships between entrepreneurial sustainability, the high cost of fuel and poor road infrastructure pose substantial threats to the survival and growth of entrepreneurial ventures in the region. Inadequate road networks disrupt logistics and escalate transportation costs, while significantly undermining profitability and long-term viability. By addressing these challenges, policymakers can foster a more conducive environment for entrepreneurship, promoting economic growth and sustainability in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Future research should explore additional contextual factors and potential mitigating strategies to further support the entrepreneurial ecosystem in this region.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results and conclusion of this study, the researcher has put forward the following recommendations.

1. Entrepreneurs should be encouraged to adopt fuel-efficient vehicles and machinery or transition to alternative energy sources, such as solar-powered equipment, to reduce dependency on costly fuel.
2. Local and state governments to prioritize the repair and construction of road networks.
3. Government should implement financial assistance programmes, such as grants or low-interest loans, specifically for small businesses affected by fuel subsidy removal.

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